

FARMERS' PERCEPTION OF SOIL FERTILITY DECLINE UNDER YAM PRODUCTION IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Soil fertility is an important natural resource in agriculture and its decline can have negative effects on farms' productivity. The study investigated the perception of farmers on soil fertility decline under yam production in Oyo state, Nigeria. Data were collected from two hundred and forty yam farmers purposively selected for the study. Descriptive statistics of means, and percentages were used to describe the data while correlation coefficients were employed to determine the relationships. Appearance of gravel, stunted growth and yellowing of leaves of crops and low yields were among the factors recognized by the farmers to be the indicators of soil fertility decline under yam production. Significant ($p \leq 0.05$) and positive relationships were found to exist between farmers' perception of soil fertility decline and selected socio-economic characteristics such as age ($p = .024$); education ($p = .007$); farm experience ($p = .000$); farm size ($p = .032$), household size ($p = .000$) and membership of social organization as well as various sources of available information. The study concludes that farmers were favourably disposed to the adoption of various soil conservation techniques which emphasize the need to upgrade their knowledge and information on environment-friendly soil management practices through the extension services.

KEYWORDS: Farmers, perception, soil fertility decline

INTRODUCTION

Yam (*Dioscorea spp*) is one of the major tuber crops in West Africa (IITA, 2009). Yam tuber is a staple food and a good source of energy derived mainly from their carbohydrate content. Apart from food supply, it has links with the socio-cultural customs of the people, especially in south-eastern Nigeria (Orkwor, 1998). Nigeria is the world's largest producer of yam, accounting for 70-76 % of the world total output (FAO, 2006). Yam is a highly demanding crop that requires large amounts of nutrients and good soil condition to maintain its optimal yield (Orkwor and Asadu, 1998). With continuous cultivation, the nutrient reserves removed from soil by yams can only be replenished with soil amendments.

One of the most serious constraints to West Africa's agriculture is declining soil fertility that contributes to food insecurity and poverty. Farmers are becoming increasingly concerned about the declining fertility of soils in Sub-Saharan Africa (Sanchez and Leakey, 1997). Due to continuous intensive cropping, farmers have experienced declining crop yield over time. Soil fertility declines at a rate that is largely governed by the type of land use systems introduced and their management (Zitong *et al*, 2003).

Traditional farmers perceive the level of soil fertility decline of their farmlands differently. It is only when farmers recognise the declining soil fertility problem of their farmlands and take individual and collective actions that this problem can be tackled effectively (Adeola, 2010). Nutrient depletion has a severe impact at the global scale, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. Annual depletion rates of soil fertility in Africa were estimated at 22 kg N, 2 kg P, and 15 kg K ha⁻¹ (Stoorvogel *et al*, 1993).

An analysis of farmer's perception of the benefits and costs, is essential in explaining why farmers would adopt measures for soil fertility improvement (Mulder, 2000). Despite the promising future of yam production, it is still beset with many problems such as excessive tillage, non application of fertilizers to the soil probably due to the level of education and belief of the farmers that fertilized yam do not produced desirable pounded

yam [Focus Group Discussion]. It is also known that continuous yam cultivation on the same piece of land without external inputs leads to lowering of the soil nutrients required for yam production (Law-Ogbomo and Remison, 2008). Farmers often have quite different perceptions and responses to fertility problems. Such situation is likely to impede the successful implementation of policies and projects to address soil fertility decline. Therefore, understanding the dynamics of these factors at the local level would contribute immensely to remedy the problem. This study was carried out with the main objective of examining farmers' perception of soil fertility decline under yam production. Specifically, the study attempted to achieve following specific objectives:

- (i) Identified the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers
- (ii) Identified the soil management techniques practiced in the study area.
- (iii) Examined farmers' assessment of soil fertility decline and restoration.
- (iv) Examined farmers' perception of soil fertility decline under yam production.
- (v) Determined farmers' attitude toward soil fertility decline under yam cultivation.
- (vi) Examined the relationships between farmers' perception of soil fertility decline and their socio-economic characteristics.
- (vii) Determine the relationships between farmers' perception of soil fertility decline and sources of agricultural information.

METHODOLOGY

Ogbomoso zone is made up of five Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Oyo state namely: Ogbomoso north and south, Ogo-Oluwa, Orire and Surulere. The study area is located within longitude $8^{\circ} 07' N$ and latitude $4^{\circ} 14' E$ with a mean annual temperature of $26^{\circ} C$, lowest temperature $24.3^{\circ} C$ while the highest temperature $28.7^{\circ} C$. The mean annual rainfall of the study area is 1,247 mm. The area is characterised by a bimodal rainfall pattern with a long wet season which starts in the middle of March to July while the short rainy season is between September and October with a short dry spell in August. The main occupation of the people is farming, but few people diversify into secondary occupation like petty trading and marketers of farm produce.

Three local government areas (Ogo-Oluwa, Orire and Surulere) were purposively selected for the study due to high concentration of yam farmers in these areas. The target population included men and women farmers registered with the Oyo State Agricultural Development Programme (OYSADEP) in Ogbomoso zone. Eighty farmers were selected using simple random sampling technique (lottery method) from each LGA using the list of registered farmers obtained from the OYSADEP to arrive at a total sample size of two hundred and forty respondents. The respondents were interviewed with the aid of -structured interview schedule and Focus Group Discussion. The schedule probed into the respondents' socio-economic characteristics and their perception of soil fertility decline under yam production. Farmers were asked to rate each crop on a scale of one – seven, with seven being the crop that degrades the soil most and one, the crop that least degrades the soil. The means of the ratings were calculated and the ranking based on means was used to compare the crops using one sample t-test. Also, a 5 – point Likert's scale was used to measure farmers' perception of soil fertility decline under yam production. On this scale, a respondent was expected to have an estimated maximum score of 50 points and a minimum of 10 points while responding to 10 statements. Descriptive statistics of means, and percentages were used to describe the data. Correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationships that exist between farmers' perception and their socio-economic characteristics, and sources of information relating to soil fertility.

RESULTS

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

Majority (58%) of the farmers interviewed were within the active age bracket of 25 – 55 years while the remaining (42%) farmers were aged over 55 years. Majority (65%) of the farmers had formal education. Most (96%) farmers that were interviewed were male (Table 1). Farming experiences of the respondents varied between five and over 55 years. However, 80% of the farmers had between 16 and 45 years farming experience. Land holdings of 88% of the farmers are between one and five hectares in size. Only a small fraction (4%) of the farmers had farm size above ten hectares (Table 1). Majority (90%) of these farmlands were inherited while about seven percent of the farmers had leasehold ownership and two and a half percent of the farmers rented their farmlands (Table 1).

Farmers' indicators of soil fertility decline and soil fertility restoration

Farmers noted that indicators of soil fertility decline and restoration include crop and soil factors as well as environmental impact of climatic (especially rainfall) factors. Among the crop factors listed by farmers are yellowing of leaves, stunted growth, crop yield, luxuriant growth of certain weeds [e.g. *Imperata cylindrica* (L.)] and presence of vigorous shrub and trees. The soil and climatic factors are soil colour and run-off. Majority (87%) of the farmers believe that appearance of gravel is an indication of declining soil fertility while equal proportion (45%) of farmers believed that stunted growth and yellowing of leaves of crops are good indicators of soil fertility decline (Figure. 1). Surprisingly, only 58% of the farmers used low crop yield as indicator of declining soil fertility.

Figure 1: Distribution of respondents according to soil fertility decline indicators

The presence of luxuriantly growing of certain weeds (e.g. *Tithonia diversifolia* and *chromolaena odorata*) was believed to be good indicator of soil fertility restoration by 83% of the farmers while, 65% of the farmers noted that dark soil colour will be an indication of soil fertility restoration and 61% of the farmers indicated that increased crop yield will be a good sign of soil fertility restoration (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of respondents according to signs of soil fertility restoration

Farmers' perception of soil fertility decline under selected crops

Farmers perceived that root and tuber crops are the worse culprits in degrading soil fertility compared with cereals, legumes and vegetables. The respondents ranked cassava (t = 104.1) and yam (t = 59.8) as first and

second respectively in the extent to which they degrade the soil (Table 2). Cowpea and pepper were the least in the ranking of crops that degrade the soil.

Soil fertility management techniques employed by farmers

Biological management techniques of soil fertility are employed by majority of the farmers. Such techniques used include crop rotation, planting of cover crops, mulching; multiple cropping and fallowing (Figure 3). Fallowing is still the most popular soil fertility management techniques employed by 92.9% of the farmers. Only 45.8% of the farmers applied mineral fertilizer to improve soil fertility (Figure 3), while 27.1% of the respondents used contour ridging to improve soil fertility.

Figure 3: Distribution of respondents by soil fertility management techniques employed

Farmers’ attitude toward soil fertility decline under yam cultivation

Results in Table 3 showed the attitude of the farmers toward soil fertility decline under yam production. Majority (82%) of the farmers agreed that soil fertility decline is a threat to yam production. All (100%) the respondents agreed that the decline could lead to yield reduction and 82% were of the opinion that the decline could cause food insecurity while 13% are undecided about this. Most (82%) of the farmers believed soil fertility decline is a resultant effect of bad agricultural practices while 17% are undecided concerning this and 72% agreed that the decline in soil fertility discouraged farmers from cultivating large hectares of land. More than half (54%) of the farmers are of the opinion that soil fertility decline is a natural phenomenon which is uncontrollable and 11% are undecided about this and 79% agreed that the decline could lead to inadequacy of land for farming. Insufficient soil moisture for crop production could be the effect of soil fertility decline as perceived by 91% of the farmers while 97% agreed that the decline could lead to expensive methods of farming.

Farmers’ attitude toward soil fertility decline under yam cultivation

Following the farmers responses to 10 attitudinal statements using a 5-point Likert’s scale, the actual maximum score recorded was 45 points while, the minimum was 29 points. An index was created from these responses and the statistics of the index shows that the mean, median and mode are 39.5, 40 and 40 respectively indicating normal distribution of the responses. The standard deviation (SD) was 4.7112. Using the normal distribution principle (Mean ± 1 SD), the responses were categorized into three namely: Upper category: 45 to (mean + SD) = 45 to 44.7112; Medium category: Between upper and lower category = 44.7111 to 34.7889; Lower category: (mean – SD) to lowest = 34.7888 to 29.

The distribution of the respondents based on categorization as given in Figure 4 shows that 82% of the respondents had favourable attitude toward soil fertility decline while only 18% of them had unfavourable attitude toward the decline.

Figure 4: Categorization of respondents by their attitude toward soil fertility decline

Relationships between socio-economic characteristics of the farmers and their perceptions of soil fertility decline under yam production

Correlations were run between selected farmers' socio-economic characteristics and their perception of soil fertility decline. Age, education, farm experience, farm size, household size, membership of social organizations and contact with extension agents were significant ($P \leq 0.05$) and positively related with farmers' perceptions of soil fertility decline (Table 4).

Relationships between sources of agricultural information and farmers' perception of soil fertility decline under yam production

Results of correlation analysis showed that all available sources of information were significant ($P \leq 0.05$) and positively related with farmers' perceptions of soil fertility decline under yam production (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

Majority of the farmers were in their middle age which suggests that adoption of innovation is likely to be higher among the group (Vabi and Williams, 1991). Majority of the farmers had formal education and this is likely to enhance their receptiveness of modern techniques of soil management. Education is an important factor in the creation of positive mental attitude towards adoption of farming innovations (Benor and Barter 1997). The study also revealed that most of the farmers had small holdings, a situation that is likely to positively influence the adoption of soil fertility management practices for sustainable land use. Results of soil fertility management practices employed by the farmers indicated low use of mineral fertilizers which could be attributed to the high costs that make it unaffordable for the farmers (Law-Ogbomo and Remison, 2008). Fallowing was a popular means of soil fertility restoration among the farmers in the study area probably being an age-long practice. The popularity of this practice may also be due to farmers' efforts to alleviate the problems associated with the high costs of inorganic fertilizers (Matatal *et al.*, 2008). Other studies (Akinbile and Adekunle, 2000) had reported farmers' involvement in the control of soil degradation using similar soil management practices identified in this study. Various indicators of soil fertility decline and restoration as noted by the farmers in the study area is an indication that they were aware of declination in soil fertility. This is contrary to the findings of Eswaran *et al.* (2001). that many farmers were not aware of land degradation. However, this supports the assertion that farmers' awareness or perception of soil problems is frequently found to positively correlate with the adoption of soil conservation practices (Traore *et al.*, 1998).

High favourable attitude of the farmers as revealed by the study indicate the important role that, yam plays in their farming systems. This perception trend could be due to the perceived benefits of proper soil management practices. Results also agree with the assertion that the utility gained from soil management behaviour is derived from the beliefs and attitudes held about that behaviour (Bennett *et al.*, 1999). The use and adoption of adequate measures to combat soil fertility decline processes could also be encouraged among farmers as a

result of this favourable perceptions. This is an agreement with the findings of Solis *et al.* (2007) that, perception of soil degradation was an important precondition for adoption of conservation technologies. Significant relationships which existed between some selected socio-economic characteristics and farmers' perception point to the fact that, the main solution to the problem of soil fertility decline lies in the behaviour of the farmer who is subject to economic and social pressures of immediate environment (Adeola, 2010). The positive association of education with the perception of soil fertility decline under yam production suggests that those farmers with higher education have higher probability of adopting the soil management practices (Odeno *et al.*, 2009). Membership of social organization had positive relationship with farmers' perception suggesting that membership of such groups could enable members to be exposed to information on soil management practices. Similar findings have been reported. Access to extension contact which had positive relationship with farmers' perception, also indicate the importance of extension to rural farmers (Mwakubo *et al.*, 2006). The positive association of the household size with the perception indicated that, farmers with high ratio of household members working on the farm are likely to embrace adoption. Thus, the household labour is the most important source of labour supply and a major constraint to the adoption of labour intensive technologies (Franzel, 1999).

All available sources of information were positively significant with the farmers' perception. This is an indication that, farmers' access to basic knowledge and information on soil fertility will probably assist in responding to the opportunities and challenges before them towards reducing soil fertility decline. This supports the assertion that education plays a key role in adoption's motivation and requires tailored, credible and appropriate information and experience that is communicated through the proper channels (Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007).

CONCLUSION

Farmers were well aware of soil fertility decline as it affects yam production and other crops. This awareness led to their recognition of the need to adopt various soil management practices that can reduce soil fertility decline. Based on their assessment of soil fertility decline under crop production, continuous cropping of cassava on a piece of land is a practice that was rated very high by farmers. This study showed that majority of the farmers had developed favourable attitudes toward fertility decline hence, the need to constantly upgrade their knowledge and information on environment- friendly soil management practices. This will go a long way in conservation of natural resources needed for food production and ensure sustainability.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to socio- economic characteristics (n = 240)

Characteristics	*Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age (Years)</i>		
25 – 35	14	6
36 – 45	36	15
46 – 55	90	38
56 – 65	58	24
> 65	42	18
<i>Education</i>		
No formal education	85	35
Adult Education	52	21
Primary education	66	27
Secondary education	28	12
Post Secondary education	9	4
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	230	96
Female	10	4
<i>Farming experience (years)</i>		
5 – 15	29	12

16 – 25	60	25
26 – 35	61	25
36 – 45	72	30
46 – 55	13	5
> 55	5	2
<i>Farm size (Ha)</i>		
1 – 5	211	88
6 – 10	19	8
11 – 15	4	2
16 – 20	3	1
> 20	3	1
<i>Land ownership status</i>		
Inheritance	218	91
Leasehold	16	7
Rent	6	3

* Multiple Responses

Table 2: Extent to which some selected crops degrade the soil as perceived by farmers n = 240

Crops	Mean	Std. Deviation	t – value	Rank
Cassava	6.4	0.95	104.1*	1 st
Yam	5.3	1.4	59.8*	2 nd
Maize	4.7	1.31	55.8*	3 rd
Tomato	2.7	0.94	45.3*	4 th
Melon (<i>Egusi</i>)	1.8	0.72	41.8*	5 th
Pepper	1.5	0.72	39.2*	6 th
Cowpea	1.2	0.43	33.0*	7 th

- Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by their attitude toward soil fertility decline under yam cultivation n = 240

Statements on fertility decline	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Soil fertility decline is a problem threatening yam production.	76 (31.7)	120 (50)	10 (4.2)	22 (9.2)	12 (5.0)
Soil fertility decline lead to decrease in yield.	86 (35.8)	154 (64.2)	-	-	-
Soil fertility decline lead to food insecurity.	56 (23.3)	140 (58.3)	30 (12.5)	14 (5.8)	-
Soil fertility decline lead to loss of soil fertility.	104 (43.3)	108 (45)	20 (8.3)	4 (1.7)	4 (1.7)
Soil fertility decline is as a result of bad agricultural practices.	58 (24.2)	138 (57.5)	40 (16.7)	4 (1.7)	-
Soil fertility decline discourage farmers from cultivating large hectares of land	52 (21.7)	120 (50)	20 (8.3)	42 (17.5)	6 (2.5)
Soil fertility decline is a natural phenomenon which nobody can put under control.	44 (18.3)	86 (35.8)	26 (10.8)	40 (16.7)	44 (18.3)
Soil fertility decline lead to inadequate land for farming.	56 (23.3)	134 (55.8)	6 (2.5)	26 (10.8)	18 (7.5)
Soil fertility decline lead to insufficient soil moisture for crop production.	64 (26.7)	154 (64.2)	8 (3.3)	10 (4.2)	4 (1.7)
Soil fertility decline lead to expensive methods of farming.	52 (21.7)	180 (75)	-	4 (1.7)	4 (1.7)

*Multiple Responses

Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Table 4: Correlation co-efficient showing the relationships between selected characteristics of respondents and their perception of land degradation

Socio-economic characteristics	'r' value	p - value
Age	0.064*	.024
Education	0.752*	.007
Farm experience	0.201**	.000
Farm size	0.143*	.032
Household size	0.272**	.000
Membership of social organization	0.129*	.021

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level [2-tailed]

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level [2-tailed]

Table 5: Correlation co-efficient showing the relationships between sources of agricultural information and Farmers' perception of land degradation

Sources of Information	'r' value	p – value
Extension agent	0.643**	.004
Radio	0.693**	.002
Television	0.823**	.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level [2-tailed]

REFERENCES

Adeola, R.G. (2010). Influence of Socio-Economic Factors on the Adoption of Soil Conservation Measures in Ibadan/Ibarapa Agricultural Zone of Oyo State. *Report 2 (7):* 42 – 47.

Akinbile, L.A. and Adekunle, O.A.(2000). Factors affecting farmers' contributions to the control of soil degradation in Osi village, Ekiti state .*Proceeding of the tenth annual conference of the Nigeria Rural Sociological Association*. Jibowo AA Ladele AA. and AB Ogunwale. (Eds.) Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile –Ife, Nigeria,.

Bennett R, Meister A and Wilkinson, R (1999). Sustainable soil management in New Zealand: Farmer beliefs, attitudes and motivations Discussion Paper in Natural Resource and Environmental Economics No. 21 Centre for Applied Economics and Policy Studies Massey University, Palmerston North New Zealand.

Benor, D., Harrison, I.Q.,and Barter, M. (1997). *Agricultural Extension: The Training and Visit System*. The World Bank, Washington, D.C.

Eswaran, H., Lal, R., and Reich, P.F.(2001). Land degradation: An overview. In: Bridges, E.M., Hannam, I.D., Oldeman, L.R. Pening de Vries, F.W.T., Scherr, S.J.and Sompatpanit, S. (Eds). *Responses to Land Degradation*, Oxford Press.: 23 -36.

FAO (2006). Food and Agricultural Organization FAOSTAT database online. Rome Italy, Retrieved from faostat.fao.org/site/567.

Franzel, S., (1999). Socioeconomic factors affecting the adoption potential of improved tree fallows in Africa. *Agroforestry. System*, 47, 305-321.

IITA (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture) (2009). Yam (*Dioscorea* species). IITA News, Retrieved from www.iita.org

Knowler, D. and Bradshaw, B. (2007). Farmers' adoption of conservation agriculture: A review and synthesis of recent research. *Food Policy* 32, 25–48.

Law-Ogbomo, K.E., and Remison, S.U.(2008). Growth and yield of white guinea yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir.) influenced by NPK fertilization on a forest site in Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Agriculture* 46 (1-2), 21–24.

Matata, P.Z., Ajayi, O.C., Oduol, P.A. and Agumya, A. (2008). Socio-economic factors influencing adoption of improved fallow practices among smallholder farmers in western Tanzania. *International NGO Journal*; 3 (4), 068-073

Mulder, I. (2000). Soil Fertility: QUEFTS (Quantitative Evaluation of the Fertility of Tropical Soils) and Farmers' Perceptions. International Institute for Environment and Development, London and Institute for Environmental Studies, Amsterdam Working Paper No. 30, 68pp.

Mwakubo, S., Obare, G., Omiti, J., and Mohammed, L (2006). The influence of social capital on natural resource management in marginal areas of Kenya. Paper presented at the Int. Assoc. Agric. Economists Conference, Aug. 12-18, 2006, Gold Coast, Australia.

Odendo, M., Obare, G., and Salasya, B. (2009). Factors responsible for differences in uptake of integrated soil fertility management practices amongst smallholders in western Kenya *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 4 (11), 1303-1311.

Orkwor G.C. and Asadu, C.L.A. (1998). Agronomy. In: Orkwor GC, Asiedu R and IJ Ekanayake (Eds). Food Yams, Advances in Research. IITA and NRCRI, Nigeria: 105 – 141.

Orkwor, G.C. (1998) Importance of yam. In: Orkwor G.C., Asiedu R and IJ Ekanayake (Eds), Food Yams, Advances in Research IITA and NRCRI, Nigeria.: 1-12

Sanchez, P.A. and Leakey, R.R.B. (1997). Land use transformation in Africa: three determinants for balancing food security with natural resource utilization. *European Journal of Agronomy*; 7: 15-23.

Solis, D., Bravo-Ureta, B.E., and Quiroga, R.E. (2007). Soil conservation and technical efficiency among hillside farmers in Central America: a switching regression model. *Austr. J. Agric. Res.* 51, 491–510.

Stoorvogel, J.J., Smaling, E.M.A., and Jansen, B.J. (1993) Calculating soil nutrient balances in Africa at different scales. I. Supra-national scale. *Fertilizer Research*; 35:227–235.

Traore, N., Landry, R. and Amara, N. (1998). On-farm adoption of conservation practices: the role of farm and farmer characteristics, perceptions, and health hazards. *Land Economics*; 74 (1), 114–127

Vabi, M.B., and Williams, C.E. (1991). Factors Determining Technology adoption Behaviour of Ruminant Livestock Farmers in Kwara State of Nigeria. *Journal of Rural Development* 4 (1), 8 – 15.

Zitong, G.Z. Ganlin, Z., Wenjun, Z., Yuguo, Z., and Zhicheng, C. (2003) Land Use-Related Changes in Soils of Hainan Island during the Past Half Century. *Pedosphere*; 13: 11-22.

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